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**Designing a Criterion for Water Redistribution in Sri Lanka to
Address the Drinking Water Scarcity in Areas Without Access to
Pipe Born Water Supply in Hambantota District Secretariat
Division**

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Abstract

With two monsoons producing 2,131mm (in 2015) of rain, Sri Lanka records around 130 billion cubic meters of water annually. Rainfall which is captured and stored by tanks are distributed through 103 natural river basins. 50 billion cubic meters of water that remains after evapotranspiration and seepage is being released to sea without being utilized properly. Divided by 20 million population, a citizen can use 4000 cubic m³ of water per year but the actual demand stands at 73 cubic meters. However, Sri Lanka is a tropical island where ¾ of its land area, 6 out of 9 provinces is climatically defined as the dry zone. Hence it is clear that there is an unequal distribution of water in Sri Lanka. Using a flexible water bag as a mode of bulk water transportation has been tested and practiced successfully in countries like USA, Norway and Suriname. Findings will depict the possibilities of using a flexible water bag as a mode of bulk water transportation to address water scarcity in the dry zone. Secondary data were used to examine the availability of surplus water in the island and also to identify

the density and discharging quantities of water from natural river basins. A descriptive methodology has been used to find the feasibility of implying a flexible water bag as a mode of bulk water transportation in Sri Lanka.

Keywords: *Water Redistribution, Bulk Water Transportation, Medusa Bag, Flexible Water Bag, Surplus Water, Underutilized Surplus Water Resource, Drinking Water Scarcity*

Introduction

Water, air and food are the three main components which required for the existence of mankind. Life cannot continue without these three basic components. Though water and food is not freely available for human kind, air is very much free but the quality of it also declining day by day due to various human activities. However, food also depends on water thus it is clear that water is unarguably one of the main basic component to operate a human life.

Furthermore, in an economic aspect, a larger portion of the world's workforce depends on 8 major water dependent industries. They are: Agriculture, Transportation, Forestry, Fisheries, Recycling, Energy, Building and Resource Insensitive Manufacturing. Among these eight categories over a billion people comes under Fisheries, Agriculture and Forestry. This itself prove how vital the role of water when it comes to economic context.

Meanwhile the importance of water is escalating along with the rapid growth of population as well. This has created both water scarcity and also the disparities in water distribution. In early stages, mankind selected water bodies to erect their civilizations. With the evolving of human civilization the population grew drastically. Therefore, with the increasing numbers people had to establish their civilizations away from the water bodies. Some countries naturally inhabited easy access to water and some could not, thus emerged the disparities in water distribution. Moreover mankind invented ways and methods to increase the life expectancy and as a result, the world population stands at 7.5 billion at present. Hence the correlation between the increasing population and the amount of resources need has triggered major concerns for the scientists and lawmakers across the globe.

Beginning of the 21st century marked one such occasion where the world identified that skyrocketing population and their demands have wearied the fresh water resource, thus the living is becoming more complex and a challenging for the generations to come. It is evident that the staggering 7 billion people is burdening the nature heavily and water being a limited resource, it has come to a point where immediate steps are needed to find ways and methods to manage the increasing demand for water. Therefore, Water Management and Development plans have become a central topic in the present context of the world.

Attempts to safeguard the water resource are being made through several policy frameworks such as Sustainable Development concepts and also through concepts like Green Economies. Further prominent legal frameworks have also been drawn under human rights to safeguard the rights of people to safe drinking water and sanitation. (*The United Nations world water development report, 2016*).

However, the problem still remains at large as world is yet to find a cement solution for water scarcity and distribution disparities. At present some countries like Norway, Canada, Alaska and Greenland have ample amount of water while countries in the Middle East for an example experience a water scarcity. Therefore, it is clear that the Water has not been equally distributed among the abundant life forms of the world despite various attempts eradicate water scarcity. However, this disparity of water distribution is not only evident among countries but also within countries as well. Countries like Australia, Sri Lanka and United States of America are perfect examples to depict this disparity in water distribution within a territory.

Map 01: Global Physical and Economic Water Scarcity

Source: The United Nations world water development report 2016

Note:**Little or no water scarcity:**

Abundant water resources relative to use, with less than 25% of water from rivers withdrawn for human purpose.

Physical water scarcity:

Water resources development is approaching or has exceeded sustainable limits: More than 75% of river flows are withdrawn for agriculture, industry, and domestic purposes (accounting for recycling of return flows). This definition – relating water availability to water demand – implies that dry areas are not necessarily water scarce.

Approaching physical water scarcity:

More than 60% of river are withdrawn. These basins will experience physical water scarcity in the near future

Economic water scarcity:

Human, institutional, and financial capital limit access to water even though water in nature is available locally to meet human demands). Water resources are abundant relative to water use, with less than 25% of water from rivers withdrawn for human purposes, but malnutrition exists.

Source: CAWMA (2007, Map 2.1, p. 63), reproduced with permission from the International Water Management Institute (IWMI). (The United Nations, 2016)

Therefore, the world needs to develop criteria to transport its water surplus, to water scarce lands across the globe. It is clear that the traditional methods like irrigational canals are not sustainable anymore as the land resource have been taken over by the growing population. Consequently, the need has arisen to find an essential solution to develop criteria to transport water in large amounts.

Sri Lanka is one such example to show disparities in water distribution within a country or a territory. According to country profile, Sri Lanka receives an Annual Rainfall (Avg.) (2015) – 2,131 mm of rain annually, amounting to about 130 billion cubic meters of water (Central Bank of Sri Lanka, 2016).

There are four rainfall seasons during the year,

1. The South - West monsoon period (May to September)
2. Intermonsoon period following the South-West monsoon (October to November)
3. The North - East monsoon period (December to February)
4. The Intermonsoon period following the North- east monsoon (March to April)

Traditionally the rainfall water was captured and stored by tanks and distributed from place to place through canals. This network is called the Cascade system. The surface water that remains, after evapotranspiration and seepage, drains in to the sea through the well-organized system of natural river basins. Sri Lanka has a total of 103 distinct natural stream basins.

Even though Sri Lanka experience a 130 billion cubic meter of water every year, it is a tropical island where $\frac{3}{4}$ of its land area, 6 out of 9 provinces and 14 out of 25 administrative districts is climatically defined as the dry zone. Dry zone has always been an agro culturally difficult area due to its relatively low rainfall and prolonged dry season sometimes spreading over 6 to 7 months (*Plan Sri Lanka, 2010*).

This clearly indicates that there is an unequal distribution of water within the country. Due to this phenomenon, inhabitants of the dry zone have less access to water. This situation has expanded the density of the issues faced by the people when attempting to full fill their basic needs related to water. Such as drinking, Cooking, Sanitary and other industrial and commercial purposes. The people who are worst affected are the ones who have less access even to pipe born water.

According to the data given by Department of Censes & Statistics only 40% of Sri Lankan population has organized water supply facilities and 59.4% is depending on other sources such as wells, tube wells, streams and rivers etc., including 10% on unprotected sources (*Gamini, n.d.*).

However, in the present setting as the land resource have also become scarce due to the high population growth rate, allocation of large portion of land space required to erect a traditional water redistribution mechanism is also challenging. Therefore, it is inevitable that the country cannot no longer depend either on cascade system or any other surface water distribution or storing systems. This situation is forcing the lawmakers to find an innovational alternative to redistribute the surplus water to the dry zone of the country.

Intentional movement of water through human intervention over as large distance is called water transportation. Water transportation occurs in both large and small quantities and methods used for this exchange falls under three categories.

1. Aqueducts - which include pipelines, canals, and tunnels.
2. Container shipment - which includes transport by tank truck, tank car, and tank ship.
3. Towing - Where a tugboat is used to pull an iceberg or a large water bag along behind it. (Malagnoux, 2008).

Figure 01: Example Flexible water bags

Source: http://static.euronews.com/articles/322071/1000x563_322071.jpg.

Figure 02: Example Flexible water bags

Source: <http://www.alshindagah.com/janfeb2002/Water4.jpg>.

Using a flexible water bag as a method for bulk water transportation was first introduced by professor William Hawthorne in 1956. He named his invention, which is a large flexible watertight tube as the Dracone Barge. It was designed with the intention of carrying large amounts of liquids for a long distance and to be towed by a ship. One large flexible watertight tube has a capacity of 935 cubic meters while weighing only 6.5 tonnes when it is empty.

The whole idea behind this technology was to carry a large amount of liquids through water from one place to another place with limited cost (Hawthorne & Swinnerton-Dyer, 1957).

([https://www.revolvy.com/main/index.php?s=Dracone Barge.](https://www.revolvy.com/main/index.php?s=Dracone+Barge)).

Next major breakthrough in the Flexible Water Bag transportation method comes in 1993 when the inventor Terry Spragg tested his model the "Spragg Bag". The Spragg Bag was 75 meters long and it had the capacity to hold 3000 cubic meters of water (790,000 US Gal) and he managed to successfully tow it in his first attempt in 1993 (<http://www.waterbag.com/>). However, in his second attempt which was taken place in 1996 where a Spragg Bag was towed from Port Angeles to Seattle, Washington one of the two bags under tow developed a tear.

(<http://www.aguanomics.com/2009/02/persistence-and-baggs.html>),

(<http://www.aguanomics.com/2009/09/fear-and->,

[watermanagers.html?utm_source=feedburner&utm_medium=feed&utm_campaign=Feed%3A+aguanomics+%28Aguanomics%29](http://www.aguanomics.com/2009/09/fear-and-)).

After Terry Spragg, Nordic Water Supply, a company from Norway developed another flexible water bag in 1997. They designed it under an agreement with Turkey to transport fresh water to Northern Cyprus. The expected amount of water that was planned to be transported by this 10,800 m³ bag was 7 million m³ of water, within two years at an annual cost of €2.7 million per year.

However, the contract was discontinued later as they managed to transport only 4 million m³ in 4 years. Following this incident, the Norwegian company went out of business and their technology was acquired by a Japanese company called the Monohakobi Institute of Technology (Anderson, T.L. (2011). "Exporting Water to the World". *Journal of Contemporary Water Research and Education*, (<https://www.nri.com/global/opinion/papers/2011/pdf/np2011160.pdf>).

In recent years, engineers from a European research project which included experts from Italy, Greece, Turkey, Spain and the Czech Republic developed another flexible water bag in 2010 and their module was named REFRESH water bag. Stage one of the project was launched from 2010 to 2012 and only focused on validating the water bag concept. Their prototype with 200 m³ of capacity was tested in Greece in 2012. Subsequently they launched the stage two of the project to upgrade and remodel their design under the name XXL-REFRESH which ran from 2013 to 2015. At the end of the second phase in 2015 they managed to successfully test a 60m long water bag with the capacity of 2500 m³ in Spain under XXL-REFRESH project and named it the Big Bag Theory. (<http://www.euronews.com/2012/12/06/bags-of-water>).

(<http://www.euronews.com/2016/01/25/the-big-bag-theory-a-cheap-and-innovative-way-to-transport-fresh-water>).

When discussing about the Water bag technology one of the remarkable discoveries was made by innovator Terry Spragg when he invented his zipper connection system which was developed by an Italian company called Ziplast. Mr. Spragg also obtained a patent for this invention which allowed him to connect water bags in long trains using this zipper like railroad boxcars are connected in long trains with coupling. According to Mr. Spragg zipper is the strongest, easiest, quickest and the most convenient way to connect and disconnect fabric bag to fabric bag. The fabric sleeved zippers can be operated manually using a pneumatic or a radio controlled slider. Bags are connected end to end using the zipper and a string of 50 bags (Several miles in length) can be towed by a single vessel. The zipper plays a major role for the success of this method as it distributes the towing force around the circumference of the bags. According to data the maximum longitudinal load from the towing force on a string of 50 water filled bags is 79 pounds per inch around the edge at the front of the bag in front.

The bags that used in Spragg technology can vary in sizes. One bag would average approximately 43 feet in diameter and 500 feet in length with the capacity of 4,500,000 gallons of water (17,000 m³). But the size of the water bag depends on the loading and off-loading requirements. CH2M-Hill, an engineering firm produced five special studies for Water bag loading and off loading facilities under the contract with Spragg and Associates and their findings on water delivery system have given in the list below.

1. Shore side facilities to handle water from the source (i.e., pump stations, water storage structures, etc.) and ocean pipelines to the offshore water-loading platforms.
2. Water-loading platforms to fill the bags
3. Bag assembly facility to prepare and deliver empty bags to the water-loading facility
4. Transport system to tow full bags to a marshaling facility
5. Marshaling facility to assemble bags into towing strings for transport to delivery sites
6. Off-loading facility to remove water from the bags
7. Empty bag handling and transport system to rig empty bags for the return trip to the loading facility.
8. Mooring and bag handling facilities in the vicinity of the off-loading facility
9. Ancillary facilities, such as water filtration plants, booster-pump stations, pipelines to municipal reservoirs or wells, and ocean pipelines from the off-loading facilities (<http://www.waterbag.com/>).

Moreover, a specially designed system of coated fabric and a fiber connection has also been used to meet the required strength of over 1000 pounds per inch for both bags and interconnection skirts.

According to Laborde Marine, a 4,300 horsepower tug with a bollard pull of 110,000 pounds can pull a string of fifty bags (500-foot long) weighing 1,300,000 tons, at a speed of 3 knots.

Spragg bag proved its viability when the engineers at the Massachusetts Institute of Technology conducted an extensive stress and vibration test on zipper, fabric and tow system. They applied over 1000 pounds per inch and it successfully survived. Therefore, a string of fifty bags have the capacity of delivering a 228 million gallons (850,000 m³) of water per trip (<http://www.waterbag.com/>).

Meanwhile the REFRESH concept, which is different from other models that was proposed earlier, is highly resistant and watertight due to the textile materials that was used to develop the flexible water bag. Unlike the gigantic containers suggested by the Nordic Water Supply or the rail road box cart system in the Spragg Bag Method, the REFRESH system is made out of series of units connected by watertight zippers. According to Samuele Ambrosetti who is an industrial innovation engineer with D'Appolonia the main components of the bag is connected with a strong and a waterproof zipper. Like in Spragg bags the zipper also plays a major role in the REFRESH scheme as well. The Italian company Ziplast was once again consulted to produce the specialty zipper of the REFRESH water bag and they invented a completely different tooth engagement design which manages to contain the strength of the original Spragg Bag zipper while adding water tightness as well (http://siswebs.org/water/story.php?title=WATERBAG_TECHNOLOGY_AND_INTER-STATE_WATER_TRANSFERS).

According to the General Manager of Ziplast, Gianfranco Germani, the seam is specially designed to make this bag fully modular. It consists of two layers of material sealed like a sandwich inside the textile surface of the waterbag. In the middle of the zipper there is a polyurethane membrane which guaranties a waterproof seal (<http://www.euronews.com/2016/01/25/the-big-bag-theory-a-cheap-and-innovative-way-to-transport-fresh-water>).

Figure 03: Testing zip strength of “high-strength watertight zip” developed for refresh bags

Source:[http://www.eppm.com/downloads/3234/download/Refresh%203%20b.jpg?cb=7fe3d8fcb700f46a7447dda14a87b422&w=426&h=.](http://www.eppm.com/downloads/3234/download/Refresh%203%20b.jpg?cb=7fe3d8fcb700f46a7447dda14a87b422&w=426&h=)

Zipper which runs along the outside of the bag make it possible to combine individual parts or join several modules and adjust the bag according to the requirement. The prototype developed by REFRESH have the capacity to contain 2000 cubic meters of fresh water which is equal to 2000 tons in weight. Therefore, the engineers need to make sure that the zipper do not burst when towed especially from a strong wave or due to high speed. In an attempt to avoid such a hazard, the engineers have applied a special device, a fiberoptic sensor inside the water bag to keep a record on the deformation of the tanks. This is a special safety function which the Spragg Bag did not had. Therefore, when the water bag is attached to the tugboat the engineers do not have to depend only on the strength of the fabric but they get the extra option to mitigate the external pressures as well.

One of the main reasons behind the invention of Water Bags is to find an economically feasible solution to transport surplus water to water scarce areas. Even though there are options like Super Tankers, Desalination Plants, Tanker trucks, aqueducts or pipelines, transportation of water through flexible water bags are comparatively cheaper than other options and environmentally sound as well. According to the associated coupler and zipper patent, for water bags to be economically feasible there should be several water bags towed at same time. The greater the volume of water that can be delivered per trip the better the economies (http://siswebs.org/water/story.php?title=WATERBAG_TECHNOLOGY_AND_INTER-STATE_WATER_TRANSFERS).

The cost to transport water 300 to 800 miles (1,300 km) through the ocean, based on deliveries of 5 million US gallons per day (19,000 m³/d) to 10 million US gallons per day (38,000 m³/d), is estimated to be between \$350 to \$450 per acre foot, depending on the length of the voyage and the amount of water delivered per trip. Increasing the amount of water delivered per day in each waterbag train will help to significantly reduce the cost of the water delivered.

Once the reliability of the waterbag delivery system has proven its economics and reliability it will just be a matter of adding more water bags to the trains, and more trains to the system in order to increase the amount of water delivered to selected locations, while also reducing the cost of the water delivered. Based on the increasing reliability of the waterbag delivery system over time, it should be possible to be able to economically deliver 100,000's of acre feet per year to many coastal locations around the world. According to the inventor of the Spragg bag, the total cost of delivering fresh water down the California coast by his waterbag technology for a distance of 800 miles (1,300 km) from British Columbia to Monterey would cost about \$966 per acre-foot per

year. Keith Spain in a study for a Master of Arts then shows in an analysis that it would save the residents of the Monterey Peninsula some \$1,134 per-acre foot otherwise using a desalination plant. This is a savings of over \$19 million per year for the Monterey taxpayers. This number assumes a usage of approximately 17,000 acre feet (21,000,000 m³) per year (17,000 X \$1,134 = \$19,278,000 savings) (Malagnoux, 2008).

According to REFRESH engineers their method is twice cheap than the water tanker deliveries. And unlike water tankers this solution is environmentally sound and water bag can also be unzipped, folded and stored in a container after a delivery.

(<http://www.euronews.com/2016/01/25/the-big-bag-theory-a-cheap-and-innovative-way-to-transport-fresh-water>).

With all this evidence it is clear that bulk water transportation via flexible water bags are scientifically possible. This study aims to design a criterion for water redistribution in Sri Lanka to address drinking water scarcity in areas without access to pipe born water in Hambantota District Secretariat Division which was identified as the mostly affected district in Sri Lanka with water scarcity.

Further a main attention will be given to check whether the underutilized surplus water resource available in Sri Lanka can be utilized? Can underutilized surplus water resource be utilized to solve the drinking water scarcity in Hambantota District Secretariat Division? And finally can the flexible water bag technology which is being used for bulk water transportation, be implemented to redistribute surplus water to the dry zone of the country? Will be examined throughout the study.

Materials and Methods

Department of Meteorology data was used to identify the, Climatic zones and the average annual rainfall of Sri Lanka.

Secondary data of Department of Meteorology was also used to do a comparative study on the rainfall patterns to the catchment areas of the Kalu-ganga (which is the center attention of the study) and Kuda Wella South GND in Hambantota DSD.

Records maintained by the Hydrology division of the Department of Irrigation was used to identify 103 natural river basins in the Sri Lanka and also to identify the river with the largest run off.

Data from Hambantota Districts Secretariat division was gathered on the 582 Grama Niladari divisions to identify the areas without pipe born water supply.

United Nations World Water Development Reports was also cited to identify the existing scenarios, trends, definitions, parameters, special characteristics, threats or challenges, facts and figures of the world fresh water resource.

Population trends and dynamics affecting the world water resource was also identified from the United Nations World Water Development Reports.

Secondary data from the internet was also used to gather information on bulk water transportation methods practiced in other countries. These data were used to do a comparative analysis to identify the positive and negative characteristics of these methods as well.

Secondary data from the internet was also used to study about the concept, technological evolution and implementation of the flexible water bags as an innovational method for bulk water transportation.

Journal articles and previous studies were referred to identify other methods used in rest of the world to address the water scarcity as desalination, Reverse Osmosis (RO), Nano Filtration (NF), Ultra Filtration (UF), Micro Filtration (MF) and water recycling methods.

Meanwhile primary data was also used to identify the district worst affected by water scarcity in Sri Lanka.

Climatic zones of Sri Lanka

Map 02: Agro Ecological map of Sri Lanka

Source: Department of Meteorology (based on Department of Agriculture)

Hambantota district is the most affected district among other districts of the island from water scarcity.

Map 03: Geographical location of Hambanthota

Source: Constructed by Researcher

Kudawella South in Hambanthota District was selected as the main study area as it is situated in a close proximity to the sea this factor is critical when implementing bulk water transportation. Furthermore, Kudawella is also one of the worst affected from water scarcity and with a less coverage of pipe born water as well.

Map 04: GNDs With and Without Pipe Born Water Supply in Hambanthoa

Source: Constructed by Researcher

Map 05: Kudawella South GND

Source: Constructed by Researcher

Kalu Ganga belongs to the wet zone of the country and it also holds the largest run off in the country. Therefore, it was selected as the main resource source to implement a bulk water transportation method (Appendices 1). Even though this data set was presented in 1974 the latest data collected from the Putupaula one of the observation stations of the Irrigation Department (Hydrological Annual Report 2012/13), proves that Kalu-ganaga holds the largest runoff in Sri Lanka (Appendices 2).

Bulk water transportation is being used in many countries across the globe for many purposes. Some countries use bulk water transportation to address the water scarcity issues within their territories while some other countries use bulk water transportation methods to address the water scarcity beyond their territories.

Countries like Norway and Suriname use bulk water transportation to export their water resource to other countries. United States of America use bulk water transportation to redistribute their water resource to water scarce areas within their borders as well.

These examples from the globe can be taken as a paradigm for Sri Lanka as well. Suriname and Norway are two countries that are open for sea and has a surplus water resource and they engage in water exporting commercially. With an annual Rainfall (Avg.) (2015) – 2,131 mm, amounting to about 130 billion cubic meters, Sri Lanka too comprise with a surplus water resource.

Map 06: Sri Lanka River Basins

Source: Department of Irrigation

Being strategically positioned in the Indian Ocean between countries like Australia and Middle East which has a high demand for fresh water Sri Lanka can take Norway and Suriname as perfect examples to engage in bulk water transportation for commercial purposes as well.

Meanwhile when compared with the US situation, where they use bulk water transportation to redistribute the ample amount of water available to the water scarce areas within their territory, Sri Lanka with 103 natural river basins and a rich annual rainfall also possess the capacity to practice the American method and address the water scarcity issues in the country.

Despite the rich water availability, 6 out of 9 provinces and 14 out of 25 administrative districts in Sri Lanka is climatically defined as the dry zone (Map 02: Agro Ecological Map of Sri Lanka). Island experience a surplus water resource and it overflows annually through natural river basins.

It is significant to examine the importance and the viability of the flexible water bag technology which is introduced in this study, when compared with the ancient surface irrigation system practiced in Sri Lanka up to date.

Cascade system comprise with irrigational canals was used to collect and distribute water to the dry zone in Sri Lanka in the old days, however the sustainability of this system was challenged after the independence in 1948 and as a result projects like Mahaweli and Gal Oya was launched to strengthen the supply of water to the dry zone in the country.

Nevertheless, such large scale projects required a large land area and allocating the required space for these projects became problematic in the last phases of these projects. And the result was underground tunnels like Uma Oya and Upper Kothmale.

But then in the present context the population of the country has increased and along with that demand for water has similarly increased. Unfortunately, the available land resource is declining thus allocating more time, money and space to develop a surface water distribution system is proving to be questionable.

However, compared with the surface water distribution method, transporting water via a flexible bag is an economically sound solution. The capital cost and the maintenance charges are minimal. The most highlighted fact is that a flexible water bag will not consume a large area of land compared to the surface water distribution system currently implemented in Sri Lanka.

It is clear that allocating more land for surface water distribution methods are not a sustainable answer for the problem at hand, land resource is fixed and cannot be propagated and at a situation like this Sri Lanka can easily test flexible water bags as a bulk water transportation method.

Kalu Ganga which starts and ends its journey within the wet zone possesses the largest runoff in the country among the 103 natural river basins. However, Kalu Ganga records an annual discharge amount of 72.4% as a percentage of precipitation while river Mahaweli records only 30.9%. (Figure 09: 103 Rivers in Sri Lanka) Kalu Ganga also receives an annual precipitation volume of 11,302 (mcm) while Mahaweli records 26,368 (mcm) (Manchanayake & Madduma Bandara, 1999).

Comparison of these two river basins clearly shows that the water of Kalu Ganga is not being properly utilized and can be used to address the water scarcity in the dry zone of the country or in another country.

Map 07: Geographical Location of Kalu Ganga River Basin

Source: Google Maps

Meanwhile in his study on Malwathu Oya river basin Nagamuthu Piratheeparajah of the university of Jaffna, department of Geography has identified that fresh water released from Malwathu Oya river in its maximum capacity (300 cubic meters per hour) is not contaminated by the salt water for about 1km space from Arippu delta and in to the sea (Piratheeparajah. N, 2016).

When using a flexible water bag for bulk water transportation, water pumping and discharging mechanism plays a major role but compared with the technology used to build the bag loading and unloading mechanism is simple. Mechanism used by Spragg bag and REFRESH water bag to pump water and to unload water from the bag can be compared to a simple mechanism of water pumping and unloading techniques of a water bowser.

Therefore, with the findings of Nagamuthu Piratheeparajah it is clear that Malwathu Oya has a 1km stretch of fresh water into the sea and such a condition is a sound background to pump water into a flexible water bag. If the findings of Piratheeparajah can be generalized, such an environment can ease the process of obtaining water from the Kalu Ganga river basin as well.

Thus it is clear that Kalu Ganga holds a suitable environment to practice a bulk water transportation method.

Despite the water surplus, Sri Lanka also have areas like Hambantota that comes under the dry zone which experienced a low rainfall and a prolonged dry season sometimes spreading over 6 to 7 months (*Map 02: Agro Ecological Map of Sri Lanka*).

Hambantota is a coastal district secretariat division which comprises with 582 Gramaniladari divisions, among them Kudawella South is the closest GND to the sea (*Map 03: Geographical location of Hambanthota*) (*Map 04: GNDs with and without pipe Born Water Supply in Hambanthota*) (*Map 05: Kudawella South GND*).

Map 08: Geographical Location of Kudawella South

Source: Google Maps

When compared the longitudes and latitudes of Kalu Ganga river basin (79°57'36.82"E/ 6°34'15.26"N) and Kudawella South (80°44'11.20"E/ 5°58'20.94"N), the distance between the water discharging point of Kalu Ganga and the water scarce Kudawella South is around 246.85 km's by sea (Google Maps)

Map 09: Distance between Kalu Ganga Basin and Kudawella South

Source: Google Maps

This locational information shows that bulk water transportation method can be easily implemented to address the water scarcity in the Kudawella South by using the surplus water of the Kalu Ganga.

It is now clear that Sri Lanka possess the availability and the capability to use flexible water bag technology as a bulk water transportation method to address the inland water scarcity.

The Discussions

When developing a certain country, a land or an area the quantity of the resources available has to be increased or the technology that is being used to utilize the available resources have to be modified. This is a common statement which is applicable to Kudawella area in Hambantota as well. Study explains that along with Kudawella the entire Hambantota district is affected with water scarcity.

Solving the water scarcity faced by the people living in Hambantota by increasing a natural element is not possible, the ancient methods used for water storing and distributing in Sri Lanka is not anymore a valid practice to distribute water sufficiently to Hambantota district. Therefore, it is clear that the country need to adopt a new mechanism or develop a new technology to address the water scarcity issue in Kudawella Gramaniladari Division in Hambantota District Secretariat Division.

As explained in the study Sri Lanka holds a large amount of surplus water and a major portion of it flows directly to the sea through 103 natural river basins, leaving $\frac{3}{4}$ of the country in dry zone. Therefore, a need has ascended to develop a mechanism to redistribute the underutilized surplus water to the water scarce areas in the country. A sound solution to cater this demand is to use flexible water bag method which is one of the bulk water transportation methods used in the world.

Consequently, Sri Lanka has come to a point where the policy makers have to lean towards developing a mechanism to redistribute its surplus water by using a bulk water transportation method such as flexible water bag method, rather than resorting to old methods like storing rain water in tanks or dispensing it through a surface distribution method.

Results

Development issues related to water in Sri Lanka is not triggered due to the lack of water availability. The problem is clearly not with the quantity but with the technology that Sri Lanka use to utilize the available water resource. Therefore, a bulk water transportation method can be developed to address the water scarcity in the dry zone of the island nation.

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